

www.arseam.com

A STUDY ON LIFE STYLE OF YOUTH IN METROPOLITAN CITY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MUMBAI

Dr. Poonam Kakkad

Nirmala Memorial Foundation College of Commerce and Science, Mumbai, India

Abstract

This study emphasizes on learning the lifestyle of Gen Y in a metropolitan city. The main purpose of this study is to empirically examine the association between the college going Gen Y's general life styles and their consumption pattern. The study confirmed that there was a significant association between gender and the lifestyle of the Gen Y.

From the study it was concluded that youth often choose products, services and activities over other because they are associated with a certain lifestyle. The products are the buildings blocks of lifestyle, marketers should therefore, have a complete idea of these changing lifestyles so as to segment them and position their products successfully. The methodology being adopted was predominantly collection of data from primary and secondary sources. A survey was conducted from 1000 college going youth aged between 18-21 to obtain empirical evidence by using questionnaire and statistical techniques.

Keywords: Lifestyle, Gen Y.

INTRODUCTION

The lifestyle concept was introduced by Bell (1958), Rainwater, Coleman and Handel (1959), and Havinhurst and Feigenbaum (1959) as close to 1950s, pointing to its potential significance in understanding, explaining and predicting consumer behaviour.

William Lazer introduced the concept of lifestyle patterns and its relationship to marketing, in 1963. He defined life style pattern as a systems concept. It refers to a distinctive or characteristic mode of living, in its aggregate and broadest sense, of a whole society or segment thereof. The aggregate of consumer purchases, and the manner in which they are consumed, reflect a society's [or] consumer's lifestyle Moore (1963) suggested still another definition of lifestyle to bridge conceptual and operational interpretations of the term. The term "life style", suggests a patterned way of life into which [people] fit various products, events or resources. It suggests that consumer purchasing is an interrelated, patterned phenomenon...products are bought as part of a "life style package".

Lifestyle is an important concept used in segmenting markets and understanding target customers, which is not provided by the study of demographics alone. Many researchers have focused on identifying the lifestyle of the consumers' to have better information about them.

In this era of competition, understanding the consumer's lifestyle is necessity for the marketers. Lifestyle is the way a person lives including the person's individual attitude to the world. Market is known for setting the trends and people follow it with full enthusiasm. Especially in India, Lifestyle depends on person's background, family, education, and nature of the work.

These days a lot of researches are being carried out to improve the standard of living especially in the metros. Websites have sprung up to good people to try out new lifestyle techniques. Consumer needs and preferences are changing, given change the factors like demographics and lifestyles. These changes can become great business opportunities for alert marketers and threats for marketers who fail to adapt. It is very essential to know how buyers behave in modern marketing field. Buyer behavior is also influenced by personality, socio-demographic characteristics, and lifestyle.

THE YOUTH

The concept of youth has been defined in various ways in the past, but today it is universally accepted that 15-35 years age group is youth. Youth can be classified in different categories, e.g. rural and urban, literate and illiterate employed and unemployed, skilled and unskilled, male and female. There are more than a billion youth in the world, and 850 million of them live in the

developing countries. Around 61.5 percent of youth live in Asia, and around 550 million in India.

Definition of Youth

There is a persistent challenge about the actual definition of youth and who they are. In the West and among international agencies, there is a strong tendency to use an age range to determine the youth category. There are at least four problems with this common approach.

Firstly, the age ranges continue to differ. A common range is 15-24, which is advocated by UNICEF and others. Slight variations tend to extend among international agencies, such as “Save the Children” age range of 13 to 25. At the same time, an age range reportedly developed by African personnel for a Lutheran World Federation youth program in Kenya’s Kakuma Refugee Camps was 7 and 40 years.

In India youth is considered to be the age group of 15 to 35 years. It is recognized that since all the persons within this group are unlikely to be one homogenous group, but rather a conglomeration of sub- groups with differing social roles and requirements, the age group may therefore be divided into two broad sub groups.viz. 15- 19 years and 20-35 years. The young belonging to the age group of 13- 19 years is a major part of the adolescent age group, and will be regarded as a separate constituency. The number of youth in the age group of 15-35 years as per the 1991 Census was estimated at about 34 crores, and about 38 crores in 1997, which is anticipated to increase to about 51 crores by the year 2016. The percentage of youth in the total population, which according to the 1996 Census projections, is estimated to be about 37 percent in 1997, is also likely to increase to about 40 percent by the year 2016. At present India has one of the youngest populations where 65% of the population is below 35 years and 54% below 24 years.

In the present study in order to have a concrete conclusion, the researcher has not focused on the entire youth market within the age bracket of 15-35 years but has further narrowed down this market by considering the youth of Mumbai within the age bracket of 18 to 21 years. To be more

precise, the study is focused on college going youth in Mumbai in the age bracket of 18 to 21years.

Characteristics and Distinctiveness of Youth

Youth is perhaps the most difficult demographic group to communicate. They not only a short attention span, but are also elusive in media consumption, fickle in brand preference and are simply challenging to engage and entertain. Marketers spend millions in marketing research every year trying to predict or anticipate changing youth behaviour. Not only does this group embrace technology at an early age, it also becomes the early adopters of all new trends and convergent platforms quickly. One can argue that whatever youth does today foreshadows what older demographic groups will adopt in the near future.

Youth are considered as the invaluable assets of every company as they are growing in market share. The word 'Youth' is a symbol of charisma and enthusiasm, a cocoon which has got immense energy has great potentials to make great changes. The youth are known as thrill seeking group, always open to fresh experiments. This cohort is healthier, more urbanized and better educated than earlier generation. Youth is also referred to as Gen Y by the marketers. Gen Y is the group of people born between 1980 and 1997. This group is important to marketers because it is next in size to the boomer generation (Baby Boomers are people born between 1946 and 1963). It is also described as the digital generation because it grew up with computers and is seen as more tech - savvy. This group is now the youth and young adult market that marketers want most to reach because its members are in the formative years of their brand relationships. They are prime targets for technology, travel, cars, homes, and furniture. The youngest segment of this group is also known as the Millennial (*Lane, King, and Reichert, 2011*). People in this cohort are also known as Echo Boomers (*Reisenwicz and Iyer, 2009*), the Connected Generation (*Johnson, 2008*), the Millennium Generation, Generation Next, and the Net Generation (*Tyler, 2008*).

This section of young population has its own identity and way of leading their life. They have their own lifestyle trend that sets them apart from the rest of the population. Some common features of a youth lifestyle are:

- More open to experimentation

- Unusual eating habits
- Part animals
- Ambitious
- Media friendly
- Lack of commitment
- Fun loving
- Highly dependent on friends
- Own latest gadgets etc.

Researchers have proved that this market is influenced by a number of factors which govern their buying behavior. These influencers are social factors (like friends, relatives and family), personal factors (like lifestyle, age and sex) cultural factors (like religion, social class etc), economic factors (like family income, spending habits etc) and psychological factors (like attitude, perception etc). Most consumer companies target this segment as they are very market savvy when it comes to brands. They are viewed as a “generation with very high buying power”

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Lifestyle

A number of researchers have focused on identifying the lifestyle of consumers. *Plummer* (1971) studied the lifestyle profiles of commercial credit card users. *Richard and Sturman* (1977) successfully applied lifestyle analysis for segmenting the users of Slimwear branded apparel. Lifestyle analysis is also used to build lifestyle profiles of specific segments like working women, *Burns and Foxman* (1988). *Reynolds, Crask and Wells* (1977) analyzed the lifestyle differences of women with modern orientation and women of traditional orientation. *Reynolds and Wells* (1978) applied lifestyle analysis for market segmentation, the development of product strategy and development of the most appropriate communication strategy. The studies of *Lazer* (1963) and *Jones* (1982) indicated that lifestyle analysis is important in formulating marketing strategy. *Forrest and Blumberg* (1981) viewed lifestyle as a principle which allowed management to assess accurately the needs of relevant market segment because demographic descriptions have proved inadequate for this task. *Ahmed and Jackson* (1979) also confirmed that

lifestyle analysis could be of tremendous value to marketing managers. It facilitated the reduction of a large, heterogeneous population into a few basic groups. Product decisions are also influenced by lifestyle patterns. *Blackwell and Talarzyk* (1983) noted that successful retailers based on general application of lifestyle analysis have begun to implement a portfolio management approach which focuses on needs of the key target markets. *Blackwell* (1980) and *Mitchell* (1983) stated that lifestyle analysis could be used to monitor changes in the population. *Aaker et al.*, (1982) endorsed the wide application of lifestyle data and confirmed its use in promotion. For *Berry* (1983), lifestyle segmentation provided a valuable insight into the task of creating an effective brand identity. Thus the study of lifestyle often provides fresh insights into the market and gives a better three dimensional views of the target consumers. Marketing managers may be able to develop improved multi-dimensional views of key market segments, uncover new product opportunities, obtain better product position and develop improved advertising communications based on a richer life-like portrait of the target consumer and generally improve overall marketing strategy.

Youth and Lifestyle

Amitabha Ghose (2006) in his article discussed the concept of youth, range of age and different definitions of youth given by different experts. It focused upon the youth market, the nature of the market, products/services the youth consumes, consumer behaviour of youth and size and growth of the Indian youth market. This article also suggested how positioning of products can be targeted for youth market and discussed different marketing tools and techniques that companies adopt to reach the Indian youth market. At the end of this paper, opportunities and the risks associated with the youth market were also discussed.

Mercy Samuel (2006) in his research article Dressing Up Gen-Next Indian Youth Lifestyle with special reference to Garment Industry: Implications for Marketers discussed the influence of globalization and liberalization, media change in the social structure, women involvement and peer groups on the lifestyle of youth and garment industry. It drew a comparison between the earlier generation and the present generation in regard to clothing and dressing. The article further highlighted how marketers can top the growing demands of urban consumers and introduce the dressing trends to the great Youth Indian Bazaar. The concluding section

highlighted that fashion is the word by which the Indian youth is fascinated. A big opportunity awaits the garment industry and those who understand it faster will be the beneficiaries.

P.K Jain and Anindita Chatterjee Rao (2006) published an article “Influence of Media, Brands, Peer group and Family on Youth Lifestyle” that is relevant to this study. In this article, they attempted to discuss the impact of the factors mentioned in the title on the lifestyle of the youth.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The study aims at understanding the profile (life style) of youth market.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The present study is based on the following hypotheses. In the light of the framed objectives, the researcher has set up the following hypotheses for the present study:

1. There is a significant relation between gender and lifestyle.
2. There is a significant relation between monthly family income and lifestyle.
3. There is a significant relation between life-style and preference of garments.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sources of data collection

Efforts are been made to focus on the objectives undertaken, through collection of both primary and secondary data. Primary data is been collected from youths in Mumbai with the help of structured questionnaire.

Sample unit of the study

Out of the universe of consumers, college going youths of Mumbai city with the age group between 18 and 21 years are the sample unit of the study.

Sample size

Using simple random sampling technique a sample size of 1000 youth comprising of (500 male and 500 female) is taken into consideration.

Data analysis

The application of statistical tools and techniques for the data collected by means of questionnaire is been classified, tabulated analyzed and summarized with the help of statistical tool Chi – Square test, Anova and Percentage method.

LIMITATION AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Following are the constrains of the study which can be explained:

1. The time of the study was short due to which many facts have been left untouched.
2. The area under study is Mumbai only. But to do a complete research a wide area is needed, so the area is also a constraint of the study.
3. Due to time, geographic and financial constraint a sample size of only 1000 youth has been considered for the study.

DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1: Gender Wise Composition

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	500	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Female	500	50.0	50.0	100.0
	Total	1000	100.0	100.0	

In the current study, out of total of 1000 college-going respondents in Mumbai, 500 are males and 500 females.

Chart 1: Family Income

On inquiring about the monthly income of the respondents it was observed that out of the total respondents, 29.5 percent were in the income group of less than ₹. 25,000. 29.3 percent were in the group of ₹. 25,001-50,000, 24.6 percent of the respondents in the monthly family income group of ₹. 50,001-100,000 and the remaining 16.6 percent were having a monthly family income above ₹. 100,000.

The profile of the youth was also evaluated on the basis of their lifestyle in this study. Lifestyle is an important concept used in segmenting markets and understanding target customers, which is not fulfilled by the study of demographics alone. Many researchers have focused on observing the lifestyle of the consumers to have a better insight into it.

Besides, in this era of cut-throat competition, understanding the consumer's lifestyle is absolutely necessary for marketers. Lifestyle is the way a person lives, and includes her/ his individual attitude towards the world. Markets are known for setting the trends, and people follow them with full enthusiasm. In India, lifestyle conspicuously depends on a person's background, family, education, and nature of work.

In the structured questionnaire, the respondents were asked the frequency with which they indulge in the given activities, which reflects the lifestyle of the respondents under study.

Chart 2: Parties / Get-togethers

The above table shows the frequency at which the youth under study party and go for get-togethers. Out of the total number of respondents, only 8.8 percent said they never go for parties while 53.7 percent said that they do so sometimes. Apparently only 5 percent of the total respondents indicated that they regularly attend parties and get-togethers.

Table 2: Frequency in Attending Club Visits

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	562	56.2	56.2	56.2
	Rarely	196	19.6	19.6	75.8
	Sometimes	142	14.2	14.2	90.0
	Often	78	7.8	7.8	97.8
	Regularly	22	2.2	2.2	100.0
	Total	1000	100.0	100.0	

The above table demonstrates that a majority of the respondents never go to clubs, and only 14.2 percent of the respondents visit them sometimes.

Chart 3: Frequency in Attending Social and Cultural Meetings

Generation Y (18-21 years old youths) shows some inclination towards social/ cultural meetings. However, only 3.3 percent of the total sample stated that they regularly opt for social meetings. 33.5 percent indicated that they participate in social or cultural meetings occasionally when they are in the mood.

Table 3: Frequency in Going for Long Vacations

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	108	10.8	10.8	10.8
	Rarely	259	25.9	25.9	36.7
	Sometimes	410	41.0	41.0	77.7
	Often	156	15.6	15.6	93.3
	Regularly	67	6.7	6.7	100.0
	Total	1000	100.0	100.0	

The respondents under the study were asked how often they enjoy long vacations. Only 6.7 percent of the total respondents stated that they go for long vacations regularly. 41 percent of the total respondents said that they go for long vacations sometimes and only about 10.8 percent never go for long vacations.

Chart 4: Frequency in Enjoying Foreign Trips

Most respondents in the study do not show much interest in visiting foreign countries. 76.2 percent of the total respondents have never gone on foreign trips. Only 2 percent of the sample embarks on foreign trips on a regular basis.

Table 4: Frequency in Outdoor Sports (e.g. Trekking)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	465	46.5	46.5	46.5
	Rarely	198	19.8	19.8	66.3
	Sometimes	215	21.5	21.5	87.8
	Often	91	9.1	9.1	96.9
	Regularly	31	3.1	3.1	100.0
	Total	1000	100.0	100.0	

The above table indicates that most of the respondents have never participated in outdoor sports. However, 21.5 percent of the respondents said they indulge in outdoor sports occasionally. This shows that the respondents are not much involved in outdoor sports.

Chart 5: Frequency in Use of Credit Card for Shopping

On enquiring about use of credit cards, 66 percent of the respondents replied that they never use credit cards for shopping. Only 15 percent of the youth stated they use credit cards regularly. This shows that a major chunk of the youth under study do not carry credit cards and opt for cash purchases.

Table 5: Roadside Shopping for Accessories

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	79	7.9	7.9	7.9
	Rarely	118	11.8	11.8	19.7
	Sometimes	296	29.6	29.6	49.3
	Often	203	20.3	20.3	69.6
	Regularly	304	30.4	30.4	100.0
	Total	1000	100.0	100.0	

Out of the total respondents a majority of the youth (30.4 percent) regularly indulge in roadside shopping of accessories while 20.3 percent do that often. Only 8 percent of the respondents replied they never go for road side shopping of accessories. This shows that youth under study prefer buying roadside accessories, which suits their pockets and offers them variety

Chart 6: Frequency of Going for Movies

The respondents were asked how frequently they go for movies in theatres. A majority of them (37.5 percent) replied that they go to watch movies once a month while 20.3 percent replied they go once in three months. Only 3.9 percent of the respondents replied they watch movies more than once a week. This observation indicates that the respondents are not serious movie freaks.

Chart 7: Frequency of Shopping in Malls

Respondents were questioned how frequently they visit malls for shopping. An overwhelming number of youth (76.7 percent) replied they do once in three months. 49.8 percent of the respondents said they visited malls once in three months for shopping. It is observed that youth visit malls less for shopping and more for window shopping and to pass their time.

Table 6: Frequency of Changing Cell phone

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Within three months	24	2.4	2.4	2.4
	Within six months	39	3.9	3.9	6.3
	Within twelve months	141	14.1	14.1	20.4
	More than twelve months	796	79.6	79.6	100.0
	Total	1000	100.0	100.0	

Chart 8 : Frequency of Changing Cell phone

In the above table it is observed that most youngsters do not spend money on frequent change in cell phone or smartphone handsets. 79.6 percent change their handsets after more than twelve months. Only 2.4 percent of the total respondents change their phones within three months. This means youths within the 18-21 years age bracket do not spend much on experimenting with new gadgets.

In the above study, some questions based on relevant parameters were asked, like the frequency in which the youths get involved in the following activities like

- Parties / get-togethers, club visits, social and cultural meetings, long vacations, foreign trips, outdoor sports like trekking, credit card shopping, roadside shopping for accessories, changing cell phones handsets and visiting malls for shopping.

Subsequently, the lifestyle of college-going youth was divided into two categories:

1. Moderate/ Modest lifestyle
2. Sophisticated lifestyle.

The review of literature has helped the researcher understand that this market is influenced by a number of factors which govern their buying behavior. These influencers are social factors (e.g. friends, relatives and family), cultural factors (e.g. religion, social class etc.), economic factors (e.g. family income, spending habits etc.) and psychological factors (e.g. attitude, perception etc.) and also personal factors (lifestyle, age and sex). Thus, to verify the existing theory of personal factors, lifestyle being an influential aspect on buying behaviour, has been taken up as a special factor in the current study.

Table 2: Lifestyle and Gender

H0 = There is no significant relation between gender and lifestyle.

H1 = There is a significant relation between gender and lifestyle.

			Gender		Total
			Male	Female	
Lifestyle	Modest	Count	243	304	547
		% in gender	48.6%	60.8%	54.7%
	Sophisticated	Count	257	196	453
		% in gender	51.4%	39.2%	45.3%
Total	Count		500	500	1000
	% in gender		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Significance. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Significance. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.017 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction	14.528	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
N of Valid Cases	1000				

From the cross table it is seen that out 1000 youths, 54.7 percent lead a simple lifestyle while 45.3 percent enjoy the upper class lifestyle. The gender percentage shows that 60.8 percent of females follow modest lifestyle whereas only 48.6 percent of males follow the same. Thus, it is seen that more females follow simple lifestyle as compared to males.

The Chi-square value is 15.017 with $p = 0.000$ i.e. less than 0.05. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relation between gender and lifestyle as observed in the study indicating that more number of females lead simple lifestyle.

Table 3: Lifestyle and Monthly Family Income

			Monthly Family Income				Total
			<= 25,000	25,001- 50,000	50,001- 100,000	> 100,000	
Life Style	Moderate	Count	231	168	94	54	547
		% within Monthly Family Income	78.3%	57.3%	38.2%	32.5%	54.7%
	High Strata	Count	64	125	152	112	453
		% within Monthly Family Income	21.7%	42.7%	61.8%	67.5%	45.3%
Total		Count	295	293	246	166	1000
		% within Monthly Family Income	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi Square Test

	Value	Df	Asymp. Significance. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	127.076 ^a	3	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	121.076	1	.000
No. of Valid Cases	1000		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 75.20.

From the cross table value it can be seen that out of the total respondents, 54.7 percent of the youth follow modest lifestyle and 45.3 percent lead a lavish lifestyle. 78.3 percent of the respondents have the monthly income of < ₹. 25,000. Also, as the income increases the lifestyle improves.

The present study calculated LBL Asso = 121.078 where the p value is less than 0.05. This means that there is a significant relation between family monthly income and lifestyle, which indicates the higher the income, higher is the lifestyle.

Observations made:

The above study clearly shows that one of the products that youth get fascinated with and like to spend on is apparel.

The Indian apparel industry has got a huge opportunity in the development of India, provided it is tapped in the right form and spirit. The understanding of market dynamics is crucial for the success in this industry.

Going by the characteristics of the youth market, there are four main parameters which are sensitive for manufacturers of ready-made garments. These factors are contemporary designs, price, quality and quantity. They act as potential influencers at the time of buying garments.

Apart from these parameters, the study throws light on how lifestyle as a personal factor influences the buying behaviour of youth when it comes to apparel. Table 4: Life Style and Youth Preference of Clothing

H0 = There is no significant relation between lifestyle and preference of garments

The present table value elicits the observation that a large percentage of the youth prefers to wear ready-made garments. It is further seen that 81.9 percent of the youth with simple lifestyle prefer wearing ready-made garment whereas 89.0 percent of the youth having high society lifestyle prefer ready-garments.

The Linear by Linear Association = 9.734 with p=.002 which is less than 0.05. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Thus, there is a significant relation between lifestyle and type of garments preferred.

H1 = There is a significant relation between lifestyle and preference of garments.

			What do you prefer wearing?		Total
			Ready-made Garments	Tailored Garments	
Life Style	Moderate	Count	448	99	547
		% in Lifestyle	81.9%	18.1%	100.0%
	Sophisticated	Count	403	50	453
		% in Lifestyle	89.0%	11.0%	100.0%
Total		Count	851	149	1000
		% in Lifestyle	85.1%	14.9%	100.0%

Chi Square Test

	Value	Df	Asymp. Significance. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.744 ^a	1	.002
Continuity Correction ^b	9.195	1	.002
Fisher's Exact Test			
Linear-by-Linear Association	9.734	1	.002

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 67.50

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

CONCLUSION:

From the study it can be concluded that Lifestyle characteristics have a great impact on the purchase behavior of the clusters. In a consumption environment, a person chooses a product or brand, which seems to possess a maximum possibility of the definition or elaboration of his life

style identity. Alternatively, a person makes a choice in a consumption environment in order to define or actualize his life style, identify it through the products chosen. It can be assumed that the individual's consumption behavior can be predicted from an understanding of how he represents his world to himself, if the details of his life style system are known products and services are selected, purchased and consumed by the individuals, in order for them to define, actualize or extend their life style identity. Consequently, this notion supports the proposition that there is a causal effect of the individual's life style on his consumption behavior.

REFERNCES

Aaker A.David, Yashyoshi Fuse and Fred D. Reynolds. (1982) Is Life Style Research Limited in Its Usefulness to Japanese Advertisers, *Journal of Advertising*, **11**, 31-36 and 48.

Ahmed, Sadrulín A. and Douglas N. Jackson. (1979) Psychographics and Public Policy Decisions: Welfare Assistance, *Journal of Consumer Research*, **5**, 229-239.

Alpert, L. and Gatty, R. (1969) Product Positioning by Behavioural Life Style, *Journal of Marketing*, **33**, April.

Cosmas, Stephen J. (1982) Life Style and Consumption Patterns, *Journal of Consumer Research*, **8**, 453-455.

DPS Verma and Savita Hanspal. (2000) Influence of lifestyles on Consumers' Buying Behavior, *Paradigm*, **4(2)**, 52-65.

Richard, Elizabeth, A. and Stephen S. Sturman. (1977) Lifestyle Segmentation in Apparel Marketing, *Journal of Marketing*, **43**, 79-87.

Roy, S. and Goswami, P. (2007) Psychographics and Its Effect on Purchase Frequency—A Study on College Goers of Kolkota, India, *Decision –Journal of ndian Institute of Management, Calcutta*, **34**, 63-93.

Poonam Kakkad / A Study on Life Style of Youth In Metropolitan City with Special Reference to
Mumbai

Bell, Wendell. (1958) Social Choice, Life Style , and Suburban Residence, in The Suburban Community (ed.) William M Dobriner, G.P. Putnam's Sons, New York, pp. 225-242

Moore, David, G. (1963) Lifestyle in Mobile Suburbia, in Towards Scientific Marketing (Ed.) Stephen A Greyser, American Marketing Association, Chicago, II, pp. 243-266.

Havighurst, Robert, J., and Feigenbaum, K. (1959) Leisure and Life Style, American Sociologist, **64**, 396-404.